

Implementing multilingual MOOCs in European University Alliances with the help of AI usage, LTI and open licenses: Technical & organizational challenges

Martin Ebner^[0000-0001-5789-5296], Sandra Schön^{1[0000-0003-0267-5215]}, Katharina Gasplmayr¹
and Behnam Taraghi¹

¹ Graz University of Technology, Münzgrabenstraße 36/I, 8010 Graz, Austria
martin.ebner@tugraz.at

Abstract. Producing and delivering MOOCs within European university alliances presents technical, organizational, and licensing challenges, particularly regarding multilingual accessibility, interoperability, and platform integration. This paper examines these challenges through a case study of the “Open Educational Resources in Higher Education” MOOC, developed with all partner institutions of the Unite! university alliance. The course was produced in all official alliance languages and used AI-driven tools (HeyGen) to generate multilingual instructor avatars for efficient localization. A key aspect of this MOOC was its open licensing approach. By adopting a Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0) license, the course materials were designed for reuse and dissemination across different educational contexts. To ensure broad accessibility, the MOOC was made available on the Austrian national MOOC platform iMooX.at and embedded within Unite! Metacampus, the alliance’s federated LMS. For this, Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI) for cross-platform interactions was used. Through LTI, course activities and materials on iMooX.at were linked to Metacampus, allowing users to access materials, track progress, and interact within a unified learning environment. This strategy supported federated access and engagement across institutional systems. This paper outlines the technical and organizational strategies used in developing the MOOC, discussing key challenges and providing recommendations for openly licensed, AI-supported, and LTI-integrated MOOCs within European university alliances. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of structuring cross-institutional MOOCs that are pedagogically, technologically, and organizationally sustainable while advancing open education principles in higher education.

Keywords: MOOCs, European University Alliances, Multilingual Education, Artificial Intelligence in Education, Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI), Open Educational Resources (OER), Open Licensing, Federated Learning Management Systems, Higher Education Digital Transformation, Cross-Institutional Online Learning

1 Challenges of MOOCs in European University alliances

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have become an essential component of digital education, offering scalable and flexible learning opportunities to a global audience. Within the context of higher education, MOOCs facilitate cross-institutional learning, enhance accessibility, and enable knowledge-sharing beyond traditional classroom settings. However, the implementation of MOOCs in European university alliances presents a distinct set of technical and organizational challenges, including interoperability across platforms, multilingual course delivery, copyright issues and institutional coordination (cf. [23];[24]). These challenges impact course development, delivery, and accessibility across multiple institutions. Institutional diversity complicates the coordination of MOOCs, as partner universities operate under different educational policies, infrastructures, and pedagogical approaches. This variation makes it difficult to establish standardized procedures for course design, assessment, and accreditation. Language barriers present another major challenge. A MOOC designed for a European university alliance must be accessible in multiple languages, requiring multilingual content adaptation. Differences in translation quality, terminology, and cultural relevance can affect the learning experience and engagement of participants. Easy access and technical integration are crucial but complex.

First, registration should be easy. Furthermore, universities use different Learning Management Systems (LMS) and digital tools, making it difficult to ensure interoperability between platforms. Without simple registration and seamless integration, students may experience inconsistent access to materials and course activities across institutions. Organizational complexity also plays a role. Coordinating multiple institutions, instructors, and administrative units can create logistical difficulties in course implementation. Differences in academic calendars, credit recognition, and institutional priorities can further complicate collaboration. Copyright and GDPR compliance introduce additional regulatory challenges. The use and redistribution of learning materials depend on national laws and institutional policies, making it unclear who is legally allowed to use and modify content. Additionally, GDPR regulations influence the choice of MOOC platforms, as institutions must ensure compliance with data protection laws. This can restrict the use of external providers and raise concerns about student data privacy and security. Certification and recognition are particularly complex when participants are not enrolled students at the issuing university or when a course is not part of a standard university curriculum. The awarding of ECTS credits requires formal agreements between institutions, which are often lacking in cross-institutional offerings. All these challenges highlight the complexity of developing and delivering MOOCs within European university alliances, requiring careful navigation of institutional, technical, and legal constraints.

European university alliances, such as Unite!, have recognized the potential of MOOCs to foster collaboration among partner institutions and strengthen the digital learning landscape. One notable initiative within this context is the development of the MOOC “Open Educational Resources in Higher Education”, which was collaboratively produced by all partner institutions of the Unite! alliance. This course was designed to be fully multilingual, incorporating AI-generated instructor avatars through the tool

HeyGen to enable efficient adaptation into all official alliance languages [7]. All course materials were developed under open licenses, “open educational resources” according to the UNESCO OER recommendation [15]. Furthermore, the course was made available both publicly on iMooX.at and within the Unite! Metacampus, ensuring accessibility for external learners while also providing enhanced learning opportunities for Unite! members through federated LMS integration [12]. A key aspect of this implementation was the technical integration via Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI), allowing seamless cross-platform interaction and enabling users to track their progress across both platforms [11].

The aim of this paper is now to provide a comprehensive analysis of the technical, organizational, and legal challenges associated with implementing multilingual, openly licensed, AI-supported MOOCs within a federated university network. Specifically, we seek to answer the following research question: What are the key technical and organizational challenges in implementing multilingual MOOCs within a European university alliance, and how can AI and LTI support their successful deployment?

2 Our case: An alliance-wide MOOC and lecture about OER

The Unite! Seed Fund project “Unite! OER courses” aimed to spread knowledge about how and where to find and publish OER, as well as the principles of open licensing, including CC0, CC BY, and CC BY-SA. For this a massive open online course (MOOC) in all partner languages as well as a university lecture at Graz University of Technology were planned. The project and development of the MOOC started in October 2023 and the MOOC started in May 2024 on the Austrian national MOOC platform iMooX.at [3].

2.1 Providing the MOOC as open educational resources

Since the course focused on Open Educational Resources (OER), publishing the materials under an open license was a given. The MOOC platform iMooX.at requires all hosted courses to have a Creative Commons (CC) license, further reinforcing this decision. Additionally, TU Graz, as the project lead, follows an OER policy that mandates open licensing for educational materials, ensuring that the MOOC seamlessly aligned with an open education framework.

Beyond institutional and platform-specific requirements, the CC BY 4.0 license (see Figure 1) was essential for this collaborative, cross-university project. It ensures maximum reusability and adaptability, allowing institutions to freely modify and expand materials with proper attribution. Given the multilingual nature of the MOOC, the open license facilitated unrestricted translation and localization, supporting broader accessibility beyond the original consortium. Unlike normal copyright possibilities or more restrictive licenses (e.g., CC BY-NC-SA), CC BY 4.0 removed legal barriers for scalability across institutions, enabling seamless integration into different curricula. Additionally, open licensing fosters long-term collaboration, allowing other universities to contribute to and expand the course. Lastly, it aligns with Open Science and OER

policies, such as UNESCO’s OER Recommendation (2019), promoting equity and access in higher education. By adopting the CC BY 4.0 license, this MOOC serves as a model for collaborative, scalable, and multilingual OER development within European university alliances. It not only ensures broad accessibility and adaptability but also reinforces the principles of open education and knowledge sharing in higher education.

Figure 1: The MOOC with the open license CC BY 4.0. Source: Screenshot of <https://imoox.at/mooc/local/landingpage/course.php?shortname=OERinHE&lang=en> (2025-02-18), CC BY 4.0 iMooX.at

2.2 Multilingual offer with the help of AI and involvement of all partners

To achieve multilingual videos the AI tool HeyGen was used to create videos of AI-generated instructor avatars. The original course was developed in German and then automatically translated into several official languages of the Unite! Alliance. While the avatars' speech was AI-generated, the other course components such as video illustrations, course texts, quizzes, and descriptions were created manually without significant AI involvement. This MOOC is likely one of the first worldwide to be produced simultaneously in multiple language versions, going beyond conventional subtitling approaches.

The process started with the development of the German-language version as the base course. The content was translated into multiple languages by humans, with partners adapting materials to national contexts. Video scripts were carefully drafted to minimize AI translation issues, AI examples were reviewed, and after positive approval the avatar parts were produced. Nevertheless, all visual design and video editing was handled by professionals, ensuring a high-quality learning experience. Finally, all materials were set up on the MOOC platform for launch (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Timeline of the production of the MOOC “OER in HE” and its videos using HeyGen. Source: Schön et al., 2025 [9]

The use of HeyGen’s AI-driven translation helped streamline multilingual video production. However, certain challenges arose during translation, such as misinterpretations of technical terms (e.g., “repository” and “Open Science”), incorrect gender-based language translations, and issues with numbers and dates. To address these concerns, base texts were revised multiple times before final production of AI avatar videos. Due to the quality of the translation and pronunciation, as well as financial and partner preferences, the Finnish, Turkish and Catalan versions used English videos with subtitles; Polish included both English and AI translations.

Figure 3: Screenshots of videos in different languages produced for the MOOC “OER in HE”

The OER in HE MOOC was made available in several languages, corresponding to the languages of the Unite! partner institutions: German (TU Graz for Austria, TU Darmstadt for Germany), English (designed as an international version for the European higher education area), Finnish (Aalto University), French (Grenoble INP Graduate School of Engineering and Management, UGA Grenoble), Italian (Politecnico di Torino), Catalan (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya/BarcelonaTech), Polish (Wrocław University of Science and Technology), Portuguese (Universidade de Lisboa), and Swedish (KTH Royal Institute of Technology). In addition, the open licensing of the MOOC allowed further translations beyond the Unite! partnership, leading to three additional versions, namely Indonesian (Universitas Negeri Malang), Turkish (Atatürk Üniversitesi) and Arabic (University of Oran 2).

2.3 Integration into higher education and learning platforms

Alongside the MOOC, an additional official university course (lecture) on OER was developed at TU Graz and offered in English to all Unite! members. This course was made available via the Unite! federated LMS Metacampus, providing learners with additional materials, exercises, and the opportunity to earn the Austrian national OER certificate. The course expanded on the MOOC content by offering more detailed insights into finding, publishing, and applying open licenses. Furthermore, the Metacampus course also regulated all organizational issues to pass the assessment for the final grades successfully.

To facilitate seamless access and interoperability, the MOOC was published on the Austrian national MOOC platform iMooX.at, while also being embedded into the Unite! Metacampus using Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI). This dual-platform strategy allowed the course to be openly accessible while still offering exclusive features for Unite! members. Several LTI test pilots were already conducted within the Unite! framework before we attempted to implement it in a real productive environment and official university course (see [11]).

Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI) is a technical standard that enables seamless integration between different Learning Management Systems (LMS) and digital platforms, facilitating secure connections without extensive custom development. It has been used to link LMS with gaming platforms [16], online laboratories [8], or library systems [2]. However, its application for direct LMS-to-LMS integration within university alliances remains rare [11]. Two components are always involved in an LTI linkage: the LTI Tool Provider, which offers educational content or functionalities, and the LTI Tool Consumer, which integrates and enables access within its environment. Users initiate an LTI launch request from the Consumer LMS to access specific courses or modules in the Provider LMS. Administrators can configure synchronization of course participants and grade transfer, as well as three possible user-linking options: (1) linking an existing account in the Provider LMS, (2) automatically creating a new LTI account in the Provider LMS, or (3) allowing users to choose between these options. This flexible integration ensures seamless cross-platform access, enhancing interoperability between multiple LMS platforms in educational networks. The set-up used in our case is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: LMS connection with LTI from users' perspective. Source: Schön et al., 2024 [11], part of Figure 6 (right)

The Austrian MOOC platform iMooX.at was connected to a dedicated Metacampus course via LTI [11]. Participation in the MOOC “OER in Higher Education” was mandatory for the Metacampus course to ensure direct integration of content. To assess the feasibility of grade transfer between the systems—both for individual activities and the entire course—support staff conducted tests using real and test accounts on both platforms. To ensure low access hurdle, authentication on Metacampus was facilitated via eduGAIN for all Unite! members. Additionally, participants of the lecture were required to create accounts on iMooX.at, which were linked to their Metacampus accounts. Figure 5 illustrates how the MOOC from iMooX.at was integrated into Metacampus from the participants' perspective. While the term ‘seamless interconnection’ via LTI refers to the intended functional integration - which indeed worked smoothly once implemented by technicians and activated by the learners themselves - the description also reveals that the actual implementation process is (still) not truly seamless.

Figure 5: The iMooX MOOC is integrated in the course in the federated LMS Metacampus (Screenshot). Source: Schön et al., 2024, [11], Figure 7

The initial account linking between Metacampus and iMooX.at was only successful in Chrome and Edge, while later access also worked in Firefox; Safari was unsupported at the time (now resolved). Grade synchronization for both individual activities and full course grades was triggered automatically every 30 minutes. A user experience issue was identified, as the LTI tool provider displayed a full-screen content page without navigation, consistent with LTI's intended design. Further testing in real courses revealed a support challenge: Staff could not track linked student accounts, making troubleshooting difficult. Despite these issues, exam grade transfers from iMooX.at into Metacampus were successfully executed, confirming the feasibility of LTI-based grade synchronization for the 85 participants.

2.4 Certification: Open badge and an Austrian certificate

Certification in European university alliances is complex due to the absence of mutual recognition agreements. Typically, ECTS certificates can only be awarded to students enrolled at the issuing university, and partner institutions are not obliged to recognize external certifications. Since no formal agreements were established for this course, a multi-tiered certification approach was implemented: (a) all MOOC participants received an Open Badge and a certificate of participation from iMooX.at; (b) students enrolled in the university course were additionally awarded the Open Badge from Metacampus, acknowledging their achievement within the Unite! learning ecosystem; (c) those who successfully completed the university course received a Unite! course certificate; and (d) as a unique feature, participants could obtain the national Austrian OER certificate, since TU Graz is an accredited provider of continuing education programs, offering a formally recognized credential beyond the usual institutional and alliance-based certifications [10]. Finally, (e) students at Graz University of Technology additionally received their ECTS certificate for this course.

2.5 Results in numbers and note on impact

The MOOC exceeded its enrolment target, with over 800 participants from Unite! institutions, highlighting the demand for multilingual OER in European higher

education. By February 2025, more than 1,200 participants are registered, excluding those who left the course. The university course on OER on Metacampus had 85 registered participants, of whom 13 completed the course (10 from TU Graz, 3 from partner universities). The project's impact, including a staff training, is documented in separate contributions [13]. Notably, KTH integrated all course materials into a 2024 Open Science course, demonstrating their long-term sustainability in higher education.

3 Lessons learned

To further emphasize the lessons learned, we highlight key takeaways that can support university alliances in developing and implementing multilingual, scalable, and interoperable MOOCs: (a) A balanced AI implementation is crucial for multilingual course offerings. While AI-driven translations and avatar-based content delivery offer significant advantages in scalability and efficiency, human oversight remains essential to ensure linguistic and contextual accuracy. A structured review process with native speakers should be integrated into production workflows to refine translations and maintain quality [1]. Experts responsible for careful preparation of the scripts, visualization and editing were therefore crucial for the professional results. (b) From a technical perspective, the integration of Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI) can provide seamless cross-platform access when using a federated LMS within university alliances. However, thorough testing and pilot implementations are necessary to address potential interoperability issues and ensure smooth user experiences. (c) A key factor in the scalability of MOOCs across institutions is the use of open licensing. The adoption of CC BY 4.0 licensing was instrumental in enabling the reuse, adaptation, and localization of course materials beyond the original partner network. This approach ensures that educational resources remain accessible, adaptable, and sustainable for a broader academic audience. (d) Additionally, hybrid certification models can enhance the recognition and value of MOOC participation. A combination of Open Badges, institutional certificates, and national certifications provides a flexible framework that accommodates diverse institutional policies. Future projects should explore how micro-credentials can be integrated into existing higher education systems to further increase recognition and acceptance.

The following table shows the challenges and mitigation strategies encountered during the implementation of a MOOC within a European university alliance, as demonstrated in our case study (see Table 1) from a technical, organizational and legal perspective.

Table 1. Challenges and mitigation issues when implementing a MOOC for a European alliance in relation to the case study

Category	Challenge	Mitigation Strategy (if)
Technical	Ensuring seamless integration of the MOOC across different LMS platforms via LTI	Extensive LTI testing and phased pilot implementations to ensure compatibility

	Browser compatibility issues affecting user experience and account synchronization	Identified and documented browser-specific problems, recommending Chrome/Edge
	AI-generated translations and avatars lacking accuracy and consistency	Manual review by native speakers and iterative quality assurance processes
Organizational	Synchronization of course grades between federated LMS systems	Automated grade transfer setup with synchronization intervals and manual checks
	Coordination among multiple universities with different policies and infrastructures	Flexible collaboration model with a shared core curriculum and local adaptations
	Managing multilingual course content across diverse institutional contexts	Use of AI-assisted translation with human oversight to maintain quality
	Adapting video scripts to avoid any problems with automatic translations	Test and develop strategies and adapt texts to avoid potential mistakes.
	Videos need to be professionally edited in all languages by experts	No.
	Lack of formal agreements for certification and mutual recognition of credits	Implementation of Open Badges, institutional certificates, and national certifications
Legal	Compliance with GDPR when using external MOOC platforms	Careful selection of platforms ensuring compliance
	Copyright and licensing complexities for shared educational materials	Use of CC BY 4.0 licensing to facilitate reuse, modification, and broad dissemination

4 Outlook

MOOCs and joint courses in European university alliances could benefit from key strategic developments. Establishing a microcredential framework at the alliance level would enhance recognition by aligning learning outcomes and facilitating mutual acceptance. Expanding the use of eduGAIN for authentication would simplify access across platforms, reducing participation barriers. Further testing and refinement of LTI could improve LMS integration, ensuring seamless access to learning resources, progress tracking, and certification issuance. OER remain fundamental for scalability, enabling cross-institutional course implementation and content reuse. These findings highlight the potential of AI-supported, openly licensed, and LTI-integrated MOOCs in fostering collaboration across European alliances. However, further advancements in microcredentialing, authentication infrastructures, and federated learning models are needed for MOOCs to become fully scalable and formally recognized. All proposed solutions are based on open standards and open licenses, supporting flexible and scalable digital education while strengthening digital sovereignty within European university networks. The use of OER further amplifies benefits, improving accessibility, open teaching, knowledge sharing, and sustainability (Jacob et al., in print). Prioritizing openness in both infrastructure and content ensure long-term impact while reinforcing principles of open science and education [13]. As MOOCs - as well as other joint courses - continue to be integrated into European university alliances, several strategic developments could enhance their effectiveness and recognition.

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